

OFF-DIAGONAL ELASTIC CONSTANTS IN FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Hassel Ledbetter and Christopher Fortunko
Materials Science and Engineering Laboratory
National Institute of Standards and Technology
Boulder, Colorado, USA

Paul Heyliger
Civil Engineering Department
Colorado State University
Fort Collins, Colorado, USA

ABSTRACT

We present an alternative to the usual rod-resonance and pulse-echo measurement methods for determining off-diagonal C_{ij} . The new approach — acoustic-resonance spectroscopy (ARS) — avoids the above problems by treating, for example, C_{12} the same as C_{11} . Among numerous advantages, ARS offers the principal advantage of one measurement rather than nine or more. The method proceeds from the premise that we can calculate the macroscopic vibration frequencies f_i of a simple-shape solid (sphere, cube, disc, parallelepiped, and so on) from four ingredients: shape, size, mass, and elastic constants. Thus, we can determine the elastic constants by measuring the f_i and doing an inverse calculation for the C_{ij} . Here, we consider two uniaxial-fiber-reinforced aluminum-matrix composites: 48-vol% boron fibers, 70-vol% graphite fibers.

INTRODUCTION

Composites force us to focus on a principal experimental and theoretical problem: How do the composite's macroscopic effective physical properties depend on constituent properties and phase geometry?

Here, we consider one physical property: the anisotropic elastic constants, usually represented as a fourth-rank tensor. Because they lend themselves to accurate measurement and calculation, elastic constants provide good checks on theoretical models. Also, elastic constants enter many aspects of composite-material behavior: stiffness-mass ratio, load deflection, elastic instability, thermoelastic stress, residual stress, sound-wave velocities, material characterization, close relationship to other physical properties (for example, thermal expansivity and specific heat), plastic deformation, theoretical strength, and nondestructive evaluation.

To optimize a composite's properties and its engineering applications, we need to know the complete elastic-stiffness tensor C_{ij} : five components for transverse-isotropic symmetry, nine components for orthotropic symmetry. Measurements of six C_{ij} (C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{33} , C_{44} , C_{55} , C_{66}) are relatively easy and accurate because they correspond to a single well-defined stress wave propagating along a principal-axis direction. Measuring the remaining three (C_{12} , C_{13} , C_{23}) is difficult and inaccurate because they fail to correspond to a simple deformation, and they require wave propagation in non-principal-axis directions where, generally, the mode is mixed: longitudinal and transverse.

If we examine the following usual display of the symmetrical S_{ij} matrix, we see the special importance of the off-diagonal entries (S_{12} , S_{13} , S_{23}):

$$S_{ij} = \begin{vmatrix} 1/E_{11} & -\nu_{21}/E_{22} & -\nu_{31}/E_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 1/E_{22} & -\nu_{32}/E_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 1/E_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & 1/G_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & 1/G_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & 1/G_{66} \end{vmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The E_{ij} denote Young moduli, G_{ij} shear moduli, and the ν_{ij} Poisson ratios, the three principal engineering-design elastic parameters.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Elsewhere [1,2], we described the materials in detail. Also, we described both the pulse-echo method (which gives the C_{ij} at megahertz frequencies), the Marx-oscillator resonance method (which gives the S_{ij} at kilohertz frequencies) [3,4], and the ARS method [5]. We obtained

Figure 1. Transverse-plane microstructure of boron-aluminum composite. Uniaxial fibers are 0.14-mm in diameter and occupy 48 vol% of the composite.

theoretical results by using a scattered-plane-wave ensemble-average model developed by Bose and Mal [6] for three elastic constants and extended by Datta and Ledbetter [7] to all five transverse-isotropic-symmetry elastic constants. Figures 1 and 2 show the two microstructures.

RESULTS

For boron-aluminum, Fig. 3 shows the ARS spectrum and Table 1 the corresponding numerical results. Also, Table 1 contains C_{ij} results by three other approaches: resonance measurements [1], pulse-echo measurements [8], and model predictions [7].

Figure 2. Transverse-plane microstructure of graphite-aluminum composite. Uniaxial fibers are 7- μm diameter and occupy 70 vol% of the composite. Throughout this study, we take x_3 as parallel to the fibers.

Figure 3. ARS resonance-peak spectrum. Through an inversion procedure, resonance frequencies lead to elastic stiffnesses C_{ij} .

For graphite-aluminum, Table 2 shows the ARS results together with those from pulse-echo measurements and from model calculations [2]. For brevity, we omit the graphite-aluminum ARS spectrum, which resembles that shown in Figure 3.

Elsewhere [5], we described the inverse procedure to convert measured frequencies f_i to elastic stiffnesses C_{ij} . This amounts to a simultaneous least-squares problem for nine unknowns.

Table 1. Elastic-stiffness constants of a 48-vol% boron-aluminum fiber-reinforced composite, in units of GPa.

C_{ij}	Resonance*	Pulse-echo	A.-R. Spectroscopy	Theory*
11	189.6	185.2	185.9	179.0
22	189.6	179.7	183.5	179.0
33	246.4	245.0	246.1	256.0
44	57.0	56.6	55.1	55.9
55	57.0	56.9	55.8	55.9
66	47.1	52.6	50.8	52.3
12	95.4	77.9	74.9	74.5
13	48.5	60.6	60.3	58.3
23	48.5	60.4	59.4	58.3

*Assumed transverse isotropy.

Table 2. Elastic-stiffness constants of a 70-vol% graphite-aluminum fiber-reinforced composite, in units of GPa.

C_{ij}	Pulse-echo	A.-R. Spectroscopy	Theory*
11	24.0	24.2	24.0
22	23.5	23.9	24.0
33	271.1	271.1	270.9
44	17.7	17.8	17.7
55	17.9	18.0	17.7
66	6.29	6.32	6.29
12	11.2	11.7	11.4
13	12.6	12.5	12.4
23	12.6	12.6	12.4

*Assumed transverse isotropy.

DISCUSSION: BORON-ALUMINUM

Our results show that acoustic-resonance spectroscopy applies to a two-phase fiber-reinforced material. The specimen shows natural macroscopic vibration frequencies as we would get for an anisotropic *monophase* material. In the first twenty resonance peaks, no spurious peaks appeared and no expected peaks were missing.

This material's orthorhombicity is small but real and shows about equally in $C_{22} \neq C_{11}$, $C_{55} \neq C_{44}$, $C_{23} \neq C_{13}$: longitudinal, shear, and off-diagonal elastic stiffnesses. It shows slightly more strongly in $C_{66} \neq (C_{11} - C_{12})/2$. We attribute the material's orthorhombicity to its manufacture: to the use of layups and uniaxial stress perpendicular to the plate.

Comparing spectroscopy results with theory — especially for C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{33} — suggests that the fibers contain a texture that makes them slightly anisotropic: the stiffness being higher perpendicular to the fiber and lower along the fiber compared with that of isotropic boron.

The off-diagonal C_{ij} (C_{12} , C_{13} , C_{23}) now seem to be known within a few percent, perhaps the best we can expect for a composite material in which various internal defects must occur. These defects include nonhomogeneous fiber distribution, nonparallel fibers, and fiber misorientations with respect to the principal axes.

DISCUSSION: GRAPHITE-ALUMINUM

The three sets of results in Table 2 show surprisingly good agreement: within less than 1% for the diagonal C_{ij} and within less than 1.5% for the off-diagonal C_{ij} . Because of the poor resonance-method results for the boron-aluminum case, we did not try to measure the off-diagonal C_{ij} by a resonance method. We did use a resonance method to measure the Young moduli E_{11} and E_{33} , and we found agreement with pulse-echo results within a few percent. (This comparison requires inverting the C_{ij} matrix to obtain the S_{ij} matrix because $E_{ii} = S_{ii}^{-1}$.) Thus, for this material, we get reasonable C_{ij} results, including off-diagonal terms such as C_{12} , from all three considered sources: pulse-echo, acoustic-resonance spectroscopy, and a model calculation. In this case, we used the Datta-Ledbetter model [7] developed from ideas of scattered plane waves and an ensemble average.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Acoustic-resonance spectroscopy works for two-phase fiber-reinforced materials.
2. Considering all nine C_{ij} , the spectroscopy results agree, on average, within 2% with previous pulse-echo results. Agreement is best (1%) for the longitudinal C_{ij} and worst (3%) for the transverse C_{ij} .
3. Surprisingly, the average off-diagonal C_{ij} spectroscopy/pulse-echo disagreement is only 2%.
4. Among the measurement methods considered here, acoustic-resonance spectroscopy is preferred. It requires a single simple specimen, no transducer-specimen couplant, and it works for quite small specimens. For measuring temperature or pressure effects, the spectroscopy method offers obvious advantages: one experimental run instead of nine or more.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Sudook Kim provided much valuable help.

REFERENCES

1. D. Read and H. Ledbetter, Elastic properties of a boron–aluminum composite at low temperatures. *J. Appl. Phys.* **48**, 2827–2831 (1977).
2. H. Ledbetter, S. Datta, and T. Kyono, Elastic constants of a graphite–magnesium composite. *J. Appl. Phys.* **65**, 3411–3416 (1989).
3. H. Ledbetter, N. Frederick, and M. Austin, Elastic-constant variability in stainless-steel 304. *J. Appl. Phys.* **51**, 305–309 (1980).
4. H. Ledbetter, Dynamic elastic modulus and internal friction in G-10CR and G-11CR fiberglass-cloth-epoxy composites. *Cryogenics* **20**, 637–640 (1980).
5. P. Heyliger, A. Jilani, H. Ledbetter, R. Leisure, and C.-L. Wang. Elastic constants of isotropic cylinders using resonant ultrasound. *J. Acoust. Soc. Amer.* **94**, 1482–1487 (1993).
6. S. Bose and A. Mal, Elastic waves in a fiber-reinforced composite. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* **22**, 217–229 (1974).
7. S. Datta and H. Ledbetter, Elastic constants of fiber-reinforced boron–aluminum: Observation and theory. *Int. J. Solids Structures* **19**, 885–894 (1983).
8. H. Ledbetter, Orthotropic elastic stiffnesses of a boron–aluminum composite. *J. Appl. Phys.* **50**, 8247–8248 (1979).